

Highlighting CLEW systems trade-offs in Ethiopia

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Executive Summary:

Ethiopia is currently facing significant challenges being the second most populated country in Africa with the population forecasted to exceed 200 million by 2050. Most of the population lacks access to modern energy, water, and sanitation services and it is still relying on biomass for residential energy demand and on rain-fed agriculture as the major source of food and income. Using the CLEWs methodology, this study aims at assessing if water, energy and food security will be achieved with the current trends and how would the system change if the LT-LEDS targets were adopted and if considering climate change projections. The results revealed a high land competition worsened by afforestation targets and reduced crop yield. Even if the current trends are able to satisfy the growing energy and food demand, they require also a massive deforestation together with an increase in the emissions and fossil fuel imports. On the contrary, if the forest land cover meets the LT-LEDS targets, the land available for agricultural uses decreases, preventing to meet the crop production goals. Also a climate change projection negatively affects the land-water system, requiring more irrigated land and reducing the overall production posing significant question on future Kenya's reliability on crop imports. It will be thereby needed to develop a solid water infrastructure system, able to ensure an effective water management and reduce land conflicts. This would ensure to have lower crop imports, if land conflicts with the afforestation targets arise, and better cope with unpredictable climate change impacts.

1. Introduction:

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia is the second most populated country in Africa (World Bank, 2022), with the population forecasted to exceed 200 million by 2050 (Ministry of Planning and Development, 2020). Because of that, in the past 20 years emissions have almost doubled, being agriculture and deforestation responsible for the 85% of these emissions (USAID, 2022). However, despite having an annual economic growth rate of 7.3% over the last five years (World Bank, 2022), Ethiopia is still one of the World's least developed countries, with a low per capita income of \$1,218 and a human development index of 0.38 (Ministry of Planning and Development, 2020).

Most of the population (78%) still lives in rural areas (World Bank, 2022), where the access to modern energy, water, and sanitation services is limited. Additional challenges include scarce access to electricity, with only 7% of the residential areas having access to clean cooking, and basic sanitation services (IEA et al., 2022). Furthermore, 15.8 million people is projected to face hunger in 2024 (United Nations, 2024) addressing important questions regarding food security. Finally, the country is also highly sensitive to climate-change, since it threatens the economy as 85% of farmers rely on rain-fed agriculture (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2015).

In order to tackle these challenges, Ethiopia is aiming at achieving 69% reduction in emissions by 2030, together with increasing the access to water and energy, boosting the crop production, achieving an 100% RES share by 2040 and increasing of 30% the forest land by 2030 (Ethiopia's Long Term Low Emission and Climate Resilient Development Strategy (2020-2050), 2023).

This study aims at analysing the current climate-land-energy-water system nexus, identifying potential conflicts among the systems and studying if the current trends (in a business as usual scenario) are able to ensure a higher energy, water and food security. Then, two additional scenarios (LT-LEDS and Climate-Change) are intended to address how the system would be impacted if the long term- low emission development strategies were adopted, and what would be the impact and the resource stress if considering climate change projections affecting precipitation and crop yields.

2. Methodology:

This study uses the OSeMOSYS tool adopting the CLEWs methodology to represent the climate, land, energy and water system highlighting synergies and conflicts among them. The baseline scenario is based on the Climate Compatible Growth Started Data Kit (Energy & Transport Starter Data Kits, n.d.) for Ethiopia, integrated with agriculture and water data gathered from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases. Furthermore, in order to have a more detailed representation of the land-water nexus, was

used the GeoCLEWs tool (OSeMOSYS, n.d.). The seven main crops (teff, maize, wheat, sorghum, barley, coffee, and other uses) were divided into high and low irrigated and rainfed in order to have a higher land resolution. The tool provided data for water precipitation, evapotranspiration, crop water deficit and yield for each crop accordingly to the Global Agro-Ecological Zones and FAOSTAT datasets.

Scenarios	Key Assumptions
<p align="center">BAU Business as usual</p>	<p>Constraints: none</p>
<p align="center">LT-LEDS Long Term- Low Emission development Strategy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residential and transport sector electrification • Reduction in the biomass use • Reduced transmission losses (from 19% to 10% by 2050) • 100% RES share by 2040 (with 55% electricity generation by hydro) • Afforestation (→ 30% of the land covered by forrest by 2030)
<p align="center">Climate Change</p>	<p>Precipitation: increased Crop yield: decreased</p>

Table 1 - Scenarios and key assumptions

Three scenarios were investigated in this study. The business as usual serves as a reference scenario having no specific constraints, whereas the LT-LEDS and the Climate-Change scenarios address potential conflicts among the CLEW systems and the impacts of considering the targets and assumptions summarised in Table 1.

The climate change scenario considers the variation in precipitation and crop yields as an alternative for the BAU scenario. The assumptions are based on the RCP4.5 moderate emissions pathway where the mean annual temperature over Ethiopia is projected to increase by approximately 2°C at the end of the century relative to the average in the 1975-2005 baseline period (EPCC, 2015). Accordingly to the Ethiopian Panel on Climate Change (2015), the mean annual precipitation is expected to increase by 4% to 12% by 2100 compared to the 1975-2005 baseline. For what concerns crop yields, considering a RCP4.5 scenario, has been forecasted national production decline of 36 to 40% for wheat by 2050 and of 2% for maize (Rettie et al., 2022). This might sound controversial if considering a higher annual precipitation, but it is linked to the Ethiopia’s sensitiveness to climate-related challenges such as water shortages, heat waves, soil erosion and droughts. The literature review revealed indeed a decrease in production for all the crops and Table 2 summarizes the assumptions taken considering Rettie et al. (2022), Tirfi and Oyekale

(2022), the Posdam Research institute, Murken et al. (2020), Tomalka et al (2020), Mohamed (2017), ECFF (2017), Alemayehu et al. (2018), and Zewudie et al. (2021) studies:

Crop	Reduction
Teff	-0.6%
Maize	-2%
Wheat	-18.40%
Sorghum	-5%
Coffee	-9%

Table 2 Crop yield decrease

Results:

Starting with a comparison between the LT-LEDS and BAU scenarios, the higher electricity demand due to the electrification of the residential and transport sector, together with a high renewable penetration, show a boost in the installed capacity by 2050 for the LT-LEDS scenario.

Figure 1 Total installed capacity for the BAU and LT-LEDS scenarios

This, together with the afforestation targets, allows to cut the emissions with respect to the BAU scenario as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2 Total annual emissions

However, a huge land competition arises if the forest land coverage increases of 30%. Figure 3 highlights the land use difference between the LT-LEDs and the BAU scenarios.

Figure 3 Land usage change between LT-LEDs and BAU scenarios (left) – BAU land usage (right)

It is possible to see that if the forest area increases, it replaces what was instead used for agriculture in a BAU scenario. The latter one manages indeed to increase the food security, but at the expenses of a massive deforestation due to the projected population growth that results in an increased food demand.

Figure 4 Crop production change between LT-LEDS and BAU scenarios (left) – LT-LEDS crop imports (right)

This high land competition affects also the crop production increasing the reliance on crop imports and proving that it is not possible to meet the 70% crop production increase by 2030 stated in the LT-LEDS strategies.

On the other hand, if considering the climate change impacts the following figures show a higher resource stress:

Figure 5 Climate change impacts on crops: change in irrigated crops (left) and imports (right)

The decreased crop yields cause and intensify land competition resulting in a growing need for irrigated land and higher reliance on crops imports since the production is affected by a lower crop yield. Finally, the agriculture sector would have to invest more on the costlier irrigation method needed for addressing both the growing crop demand and decreased land availability.

4. Discussion:

The results of the CLEW system in Ethiopia revealed a high land competition and resource use especially if considering climate change impacts. Even if the current trends are able to satisfy the growing energy and food demand, they require also a massive

deforestation together with an increase in the emissions and fossil fuel imports. When the Long Term- Low Emission development Strategies are put in place the growing electricity demand requires a higher installed capacity, which contributes to decrease the emissions due to the 100% RES share and electrification of the residential and transport sectors which allow to positively reduce the biomass use and its environmental implications. However, if the afforestation target is put in place, the land available for agricultural uses decreases, preventing the 70% crop production increase by 2030 stated in the LT-LEDS. On the other hand, climate change affects the water-land nexus, since a lower crop yield results in a higher resource stress, since more irrigated crops are needed in order to boost production. Finally, none of the two scenarios can ensure a higher food security, since in both cases the country will be highly dependent on crops imports, posing significant question on the future resource management of Ethiopia.

However, this study is a simplified representation the CLEW system of Ethiopia. Future developments should embed a more detailed final demand together with the implication of other climate change impacts such as droughts and floodings. This might be done through a seasonal representation of the crop yield that might for instance vary accordingly to the month considered. Finally, this study does not consider the impact on the hydro power plants, which are the main energy source in the country. Another potential area for future research could thereby be to consider the hydro power plants capacity factor variation for each season.

5. Conclusion:

The objective of this study is to assess if water, energy and food security will be achieved with the current trends and how would the CLEW system change if the long term- low emission development strategies would be adopted. Additionally, has been analyzed the impact of climate change projections affecting rainfalls and crop yields.

The current trends are able to meet the growing water, energy and food demand at the expense of the environment since a high deforestation would be needed together with increased fossil fuel imports that will harm the environment with significant GHG emissions. The LT-LEDS targets are able to mitigate the environmental impact, cutting the emissions thanks to a higher RES penetration, electrification rate and afforestation. However, this increases the land competition, preventing from meeting the ambitious target of increasing the crop production of 70% by 2030. On the other hand, in terms of climate change, reduced crop yields have also a significant impact on the CLEW systems. More land will indeed require to be converted into irrigated land, to tackle the production losses caused by the crop yield. Nevertheless, the boost in the costlier irrigated crops is still not enough for meeting the increased production targets.

Overall, this simplified CLEWs model, highlights the important trade-offs that need to be considered if planning a sustainable development plan for Ethiopia. In order to meet the afforestation targets and promote crop production, it is important to develop a solid water infrastructure system, able to ensure an effective water management and reduce land conflicts. This will ensure to have lower crop imports if land conflicts with the afforestation targets arises and better cope with unpredictable climate change impacts.

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